

BENDING BEHAVIOR OF 3D-PRINTING BIO-SOURCED PLA/FLAX COMPOSITE SANDWICH WITH DIFFERENT CORE GEOMETRIES: EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSES

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich structures are widely used in engineering applications due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, especially in the building materials, automotive component, ships structure and other daily use. This study investigates the mechanical bending behaviour of bio-sourced PLA/Flax composite sandwich fabricated by 3D printing, focusing on the influence of different core geometries. In this work, biodegradable polylactic acid (PLA) was used as the matrix, reinforced with flax fibres to improve mechanical performance. Various 3D-printed sandwich with different core geometries, including sinusoidal, triangular, double triangular and trapezoid were evaluated under 3-point bending tests.

Although various sandwich core structures have been extensively studied in recent years, contributions specifically dedicated to the development and investigation of biosourced sandwich materials with different core architectures remain rather limited. It is in this context that our work is positioned. It aims to compare different biosourced structures while keeping their relative density and thus their mass constant. With this in mind, the specimens were designed with the same mass requiring the development of a calculation method with both mutable and immutable parameters. Four different core geometries, i.e., sinusoidal (SN), triangular (TR), double triangular (DT), and trapezoidal (TP) were identified as representative sandwich structures capable of optimizing their performance. Consequently, these four geometries were subjected to the optimization program to ensure that their dimensions satisfied the above-mentioned iso-mass condition.

Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) is widely used in PLA material manufacturing. A method called continuous extrusion printing, which is an optimization of FDM printing, was proposed and used in this study. This method enables uninterrupted material extrusion throughout the process, producing the part continuously until it is fully manufactured. Five samples of each core geometry were fabricated using this continuous extrusion printing technique. Mechanical tests of 3-point-bending were conducted on these specimens according to the ASTM C393 standard. The results showed that the bending performance significantly varied with the core geometry. It is observed that the DT structure outperforms the other three structures both in terms of maximum load and fitted stiffness, which gives a new guidance for choosing different core geometries sandwich structure for isomass.

1 INTRODUCTION

The needs for more environmentally friendly products in the industry are in strong growth. Sandwich structures have long been recognized for their remarkable combination of high stiffness, strength, and low weight, making them indispensable in a wide range of engineering applications [1]. Their ability to efficiently hold mechanical loads while minimizing material usage has driven continuous innovation in the design and fabrication. The fundamental concept of a sandwich structure relies on relatively thin, stiff face sheets bonded to a lightweight core. At the same time, the fabrication process FDM is widely used in PLA material manufacturing [2].

While numerous studies have investigated sandwich structures with synthetic cores [3], the exploration of 3D-printed bio-sourced sandwich composites remains limited, particularly in terms of systematically evaluating the influence of different core geometries. Indeed, most comparative studies do not account for differences in relative density or mass, making it difficult to isolate the effects of geometry alone. Recognizing this gap, the present work aims to advance the understanding of bio-based sandwich structures by proposing a comparative experimental framework in which the mass of each specimen is held constant. This approach requires the development of a tailored optimization methodology that adjusts the dimensions of each core geometry to satisfy the iso-mass criterion while preserving their functional integrity.

Specifically, this study investigates the bending behaviour of 3D-printed PLA/flax composite sandwich structures incorporating four representative core geometries: sinusoidal (SN), triangular (TR), double triangular (DT), and trapezoidal (TP). These geometries were selected based on their potential to enhance load distribution, increase energy absorption, and improve overall mechanical performance. Five specimens for each configuration were fabricated using continuous extrusion printing. Mechanical tests of 3-point-bending were conducted on these specimens according to the ASTM C393 standard [4].

This research contributes to the growing of knowledge on sustainable, high-performance materials by demonstrating that 3D-printed PLA/flax sandwich structures can achieve competitive mechanical properties while leveraging renewable resources and environmentally friendly manufacturing methods. By systematically isolating the effects of geometry under isomass conditions, the study establishes a foundation for future work aimed at sandwich architectures to specific engineering requirements. Furthermore, the application of continuous extrusion printing paves the way for scalable production of biosourced composite components with enhanced structural integrity and minimized waste.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Isomass calculate method

In prior research on sandwich composites, various core structures such as corrugated, honeycomb and lattice geometries were classified and studied extensively. These studies often focused on characterizing core geometries at different relative densities. However, direct comparisons between different core topologies with identical relative density remain limited.

In this study, four distinct core geometries were selected as representative sandwich structures: sinusoidal (SN), triangular (TR), double triangular (DT), and trapezoidal (TP). To ensure fair comparison and minimize the influence of density differences, all cores were designed to maintain the same relative density, thereby ensuring equivalent mass. The three external dimensions—length (L), width (b), and height (h)—serve as the foundation for the geometric description.

However, these dimensions alone do not capture the internal architecture, including the morphology, the number of repeating cells, and the material distribution along each axis. Therefore, two additional parameters were introduced to precisely define internal geometry in a unified way across all topologies:

- m , the number of representative elements, corresponding to the count of repeating motifs (waves, meshes, or cells) along the length L .
- n , the integer number of full extrusions across the width b , ensuring compatibility with the continuous extrusion strategy.

This approach was designed to balance generality and parsimony: the same (m, n) pair applies consistently to all four core types, facilitating cross-comparison while limiting the number of independent variables. As a result, the minimal parameter set $\{L, b, h, m, n\}$ fully defines both the external and internal geometry and underpins subsequent calculations of volume, mass, and FDM print paths.

Due to the high number of variables, the height h and width b were defined based on dimensions suitable for later mechanical testing. If the resulting dimensions proved acceptable, they were directly validated; otherwise, additional iterative calculations were required. Python was chosen as the computational tool because of its simplicity, extensive scientific libraries, flexibility, and strong community support. Ultimately, final solutions were obtained and are presented in Table 1. All four core geometries share identical L , b , and h values—considered the principal parameters—while adopting

distinct m and n values to maintain nearly identical core volumes and thus constant mass. Note that the volumes fluctuate by a maximum of 2% from the average volume, which is very acceptable. Additionally, a 1.6 mm skin was incorporated into each design to enable subsequent study of complete sandwich structure properties in later subsection. The final dimensions were set at 138.56 mm length, 30.00 mm height, and 30.00 mm width, maintaining equal mass and relative density across all geometries.

Core type	L (mm)	b (mm)	h (mm)	n	m	V (mm ³)
SN				2	9	27196.17
TR	138.56	30.00	30.00	2	9	26759.73
DT				2	8	26604.30
TP				3	6	26132.46

Table 1: Solution of different core geometries sandwich structures in isomass

2.2 Fabrication processing

Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) is one of the most common additive manufacturing techniques for thermoplastics. This method offers precise control over temperature, feed rate, and layer height, enabling the use of standard polymers like PLA as well as fiber-reinforced composites. Its flexibility and moderate cost make it widely used for prototyping and producing functional components in small series.

In this study, PLA reinforced with flax fibres was used, supplied by Nanovia Company. Printing was carried out on a Raise3D N2 printer. After loading the filament and heating the nozzle, material was deposited layer by layer onto the heated platform. Each pass in the X - Y plane formed a cross-section, followed by an upward Z increment until the part was complete and the thermal bonding ensured cohesion between layers. A custom MATLAB script was developed to regenerate G-code with higher precision comparing with the traditional way of slicing CAD model into G-code.

2.3 Assembly and 3-point-bending experiment

To study the different core geometries sandwich structures, three-point bending tests were performed on as-printed specimens, using an Instron universal testing machine. The experimental setup, illustrated in Figure 1, consists of a cylindrical punch with a diameter of 25mm and two cylindrical supports of the same diameter, spaced 100mm apart, in accordance with ASTM C393 standard.

The tests were conducted under displacement control with velocity of 1 mm/min, under standard atmospheric conditions and ambient temperature. The applied load and the displacement of the punch were recorded by the machine's integrated sensors.

Figure 1: Experimental setup for the 3-point-bending tests on the composite DT structure

3 FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION

Finite element analysis was performed to predict the composite sandwich structures with the same relative density and different core geometries were established using the finite element software ABAQUS 2020 (Dassault Systems). The CAD models of the four sandwich configurations - SN, TR, DT and TP cores - were created in Dassault CATIA based on the geometric parameters computed in Section 2.1. These models incorporated identical overall dimensions and relative densities to isolate the effect of core topology. The CAD assemblies were then imported into ABAQUS for meshing and simulation setup.

To replicate the experimental setup accurately, three loading cylinders were also modelled: one representing the upper loading punch and two representing the lower supports. Each cylinder had a diameter of 25 mm and was positioned in accordance with the ASTM C393 standard. The lower support cylinders were fully fixed, while the upper cylinder was assigned a reference point at its centre to which the displacement boundary condition was applied. A prescribed vertical displacement along the Z-axis was imposed on this reference point to simulate loading.

The sandwich structures and cylinders were discretized using 8-node linear hexahedral elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). A mesh convergence study was conducted to ensure that the element size provided a balance between computational efficiency and solution accuracy. Contact interactions were defined between the surfaces of the cylinders and the sandwich specimens using a surface-to-surface contact formulation, with a friction coefficient specified based on the literature for PLA-based composites. The material constitutive behaviour and parameters used in the simulation were derived from the constitutive relationships obtained through compression tests conducted on standard cylindrical specimens.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The comparative testing of the four core geometries under 3-point-bending highlights distinct mechanical behaviour curves, thereby providing valuable insights for design choices depending on the intended applications, as shown in Figure 2. The DT configuration, characterized by the highest stiffness and maximum load, exhibits excellent load-bearing capacity. However, its failure is more abrupt, and its elongation is limited. Consequently, it is better suited for situations requiring high load support with

low tolerance for deformation.

The TR geometry demonstrates stiffness and strength levels comparable to those of the DT configuration while offering slightly greater ductility, thereby representing a relevant compromise when moderate displacements are acceptable without compromising load capacity. In contrast, the TP structure displays the lowest stiffness and maximum load but has by far the highest displacement at failure among all configurations. This capacity for gradual deformation and energy absorption prior to failure makes it a suitable candidate for applications involving impact protection, damping, or energy dissipation. The SN configuration occupies an intermediate position: neither the stiffest nor the most ductile, it constitutes a balanced and potentially more cost-effective solution for conventional applications in which the requirements for load-bearing capacity and energy absorption remain moderate.

These curves show that if the design objective is high load-bearing capacity with limited concern for large displacements, the DT configuration performs better. Conversely, if the application requires greater deformation tolerance, like the ability to undergo larger displacements prior to failure, the TP configuration offers advantages despite its lower maximum strength.

Figure 2: Load–displacement curves of four core geometries under 3-points-bending tests

The radar chart depicted in Figure 3 comparing the mechanical performance of the four core geometries across five normalized parameters: stiffness (E), elastic limit force (F_e), maximum force (F_{max}), maximum displacement (d_{max}), and elastic displacement (d_e). The DT configuration consistently shows the highest normalized values of stiffness and force capacities, with d_e reaching approximately 0.85, indicating superior resistance and load-bearing performance. In contrast, the TP geometry exhibits the greatest maximum displacement and elastic displacement, suggesting higher deformability under loading conditions. The TR shows intermediate stiffness and force values, with E near 0.65, d_{max} of about 0.5 and F_e about 0.75, while SN combines a stiffness of about 0.5, d_{max} of

about 0.6 and F_e around 0.55. Both configurations maintain moderate levels. Overall, this visualization underscores the distinct mechanical behavior of each design, supporting the selection of an appropriate core geometry depending on whether stiffness or deformability is prioritized, particularly if the design objective is high load-bearing capacity with limited concern for large displacements.

Figure 3: Radar of mechanical performance of four core geometries under 3-points-bending tests

The finite element simulations model accurately characterizes the load-displacement from the elastic stage up to fracture. By comparing the experimental responses with the simulation results shown in Figure 4, the numerical model was effectively validated. It is worth noting that the experimental and numerical curves are identical for stiffness, while a discrepancy of less than 15% is observed for maximum force (for 3 out of 4 configurations).

Figure 4: Comparison of FEM and EXP for Maximum Force and Fitted Stiffness with four different patterns

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the mechanical bending behaviour of 3D-printed bio-sourced PLA/flax composite sandwich structures with four distinct core geometries while maintaining identical mass and

relative density. Through both experimental three-point bending tests and finite element simulations, significant differences in mechanical performance were observed among the configurations.

The double triangular (DT) core exhibited the highest stiffness and maximum load capacity, making it an optimal solution for applications requiring high load-bearing performance with minimal deformation. The triangular (TR) geometry offered a comparable strength profile while demonstrating slightly greater ductility, providing a balanced compromise between stiffness and tolerance to deformation. The trapezoidal (TP) core achieved the highest displacement before failure, indicating superior energy absorption and suitability for impact protection or damping applications despite its lower maximum strength. Finally, the sinusoidal (SN) core presented intermediate properties, offering a practical balance between load capacity and deformability.

Overall, this work highlights the critical role of core geometry in tailoring the mechanical properties of sandwich composites. The findings provide valuable guidance for selecting core designs in lightweight structural components where specific performance trade-offs between stiffness, strength, and ductility are required. In addition, finite element modelling conducted in ABAQUS provided comparative simulations that closely matched the experimental results, validating the mechanical behavior of the sandwich structures and supporting the robustness of the proposed design approach.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V. Birman and G. A. Kardomateas, "Review of current trends in research and applications of sandwich structures," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 142, pp. 221–240, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.01.027.
- [2] J. M. Chacón, M. A. Caminero, E. García-Plaza, and P. J. Núñez, "Additive manufacturing of PLA structures using fused deposition modelling: Effect of process parameters on mechanical properties and their optimal selection," *Materials & Design*, vol. 124, pp. 143–157, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2017.03.065.
- [3] A. J. R. Lasprilla, G. A. R. Martinez, B. H. Lunelli, A. L. Jardini, and R. M. Filho, "Poly-lactic acid synthesis for application in biomedical devices — A review," *Biotechnology Advances*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 321–328, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.biotechadv.2011.06.019.
- [4] D30 Committee, *Test Method for Core Shear Properties of Sandwich Constructions by Beam Flexure*. doi: 10.1520/C0393_C0393M-11.

Bending Behavior of 3D Printing Bio-sourced PLA/flax Composite Sandwich with Different Core Geometries

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This study investigates the bending behaviour of bio-sourced PLA/Flax composite sandwich structures manufactured by 3D printing. To ensure a fair comparison, four core geometries – sinusoidal (SN), triangular (TR), double triangular (DT), and trapezoidal (TP) were designed with identical mass. A continuous extrusion printing technique, optimized from conventional FDM, enabled uninterrupted material deposition and high-quality fabrication. Five samples of each geometry were produced and tested under 3-point bending according to ASTM C393. The experimental results revealed that core geometry strongly affects mechanical performance. Among all configurations, the double triangular structure achieved the highest stiffness and maximum load capacity. These findings provide valuable insights for selecting and optimizing core designs in lightweight sandwich structures where both mechanical efficiency and sustainability are essential considerations.

Materials and Experiments

Figure 1. The 3D printing setup: schematic diagram

Figure 2. The illustration of the steps regenerated by the MATLAB code for the four core geometries (left) and the image of samples printed by continuous extrusion printing (right)

Figure 3. Experimental setup for the 3-point bending tests on the composite structure

Results

Figure 4. Load-displacement curves of four core geometries under 3-points-bending tests

Figure 5. Fitted stiffness (kN/mm) and maximum load (kN) of four different patterns with error bar

Figure 6. Radar of mechanical performance of four core geometries under 3-point bending tests

- ➔ **SN Configuration**
 - Intermediate stiffness and ductility
 - Suitable for applications requiring balanced performance
- ➔ **TR Configuration**
 - Slightly greater ductility
 - Balanced compromise between rigidity and deformability
- ➔ **DT Configuration**
 - Highest stiffness and load capacity
 - Minimal elongation before failure
 - Suitable for high-load applications with limited deformation
- ➔ **TP Configuration**
 - Lowest stiffness and load capacity
 - Greatest displacement before failure

Figure 7. Comparison of FEM and EXP for Maximum Force and Fitted Stiffness with four different patterns

- ➔ **Finite Element Simulation Validation**
 - Numerical model accurately reproduced load-displacement curves
 - Simulations validated by comparison with experimental data

Perspectives

- Analysis of acoustic emission signals and microscopic observations to identify the damage mechanisms.
- Study of ageing, as it is particularly relevant for natural fiber composites.